

A REVIEW OF HISTORY OF SECOND LANGUAGE LEARNING MOTIVATION THEORIES

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ABSTRACT

The motivation plays a very important role in the successful of language learning process. Fully knowing the the existing and existed theories in order of time can help learner and teacher deeply understand the evolution of motivations. By paying attention to every aspect which mentioned in the previous research can affect learning process, teachers and learners can choose the most suitable way to motivate their students or themselves to improve the learning process. This review is written in goal of contributing to the development of language learning and teaching through providing the information of the evolution of language learning motivation theories.

Key words: motivation, review, theory

1 INTRODUCTION

Motivation is a very old term and all the teachers and learners are familiar with it nowadays. But the using of motivation in teaching and learning is almost adapting the methods and specific materials on teaching and learning process. Actually, the meaning of the term “motivation” involve to many facets through which researchers, learners and teachers can get the overview on factors which really affect the learners’ performances and make decision to have any changes to learning and teaching process. These facts include: educational, social and cognitive psychology; general educational, social theories and sociolinguistic theories (Keblawi. 2009). These systematic base of knowledge is the result of long process of development.

2 THE BASIC DEFINITION OF MOTIVATION

According to *Wikipedia*, Motivation is defined as “the reason for people actions, desires and needs, the motivation is also one’s direction to behavior, or what cause a person to want to repeat a behavior” (Motivation, n.d.). This term also has mean of “A reason or reasons for acting or behaving in a particular way” or “Desire or willingness to do something; enthusiasm” in *Oxford Dictionaries* (Motivation, n.d.). In educational perspectives, the motivation focus on factors can affects to language learning process, according to Meece (2014), motivation is defined in many ways included: inner forces, enduring traits behavioral responses and the ultimate goal of them is to stimulate the learners to improve the learning performance. Above are some definition about the “motivation”. Actually, there is very little evidences which present agreements about the meaning of this term in the previous literature Dörnyei, (1998:117) comments, “Although ‘motivation’ is a term frequently used in both educational and research contexts, it is rather

surprising how little agreement there is in the literature with regard to the exact meaning of the concept". Renschler, (1992) and other researchers disagreed on motivation's components and the functions of this components, from the individual differences to situation differences, social and cultural factors. The confusion in defining of the term "motivation" is mainly caused by the wide ranges of components and aspects this term involves. In the dimension of this review, motivation will be considered as the methods, the ways, the theories or the approaches to improve the linguistic proficiency of language learners.

In this term meaning, the motivation can significantly affect the success of learning or not and the motivator must be one of certain roles of teachers. Even the learners must look for the fully understanding of this sections to improve the self-learning process.

3 THE HISTORY OF DEVELOPMENT OF LANGUAGE LEARNING THEORIES

There are many theories are presented from the dawn of motivation evolution. However, many researchers have the same ideas that one of the research began the modern motivation theories is *Attitudes and motivation in second language learning* of Gardner and Lambert (1972). This research is mentioned by Guerrero (2015) and Toni (2012) in their review about the history of motivation in language learning. And they agreed with Dörnyei (as cited in Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2011), from the research mentioned over there are three periods of evolution of motivation. These are: the social psychological period, the cognitive-situated period, and the process-oriented period.

3.1 The first period: The social psychological period (1959-1990)

This period is named after one of the typical theory in this period: social psychological Gardner's theory of motivation (Orío, 2012) and another is the "linguistics self – confident" theory of Clément (as cited in Kiil Molberg, 2010).

Social psychological Gardner's theory of motivation was created and developed based on the bilingual context in Canada from 1959 – 1990 under the creation of the socio-educational model. This model was designed by R.C. Gardner with the perspective that the most important factors that affect the ability to learn language were not only their aptitude and competency but the individual's characteristics. Gardner, R. C. (2010) also stated that another thing had to be considered to affect the language acquisition is the social context, which could make some changes in the learners' attitude toward the second language learning, and even made them feel interesting with language learning. With this statement, Gardner, R. C. (2010) negated the previous way of thinking that the learners' aptitude is the only factor that needed to be considered. The differences in learners' reaction attitude toward language learning based on their characteristics is what teachers need to carefully considered to have suitable changes in teaching process.

The creation of socio-educational model places the first step to the term "motivation" because of its two main factors which needed to observe: aptitude and effects from social and environmental context. Even Gardner, R. C. (2010) put more attention in the second factors because of his

interesting in how can a language learner successfully acquire second language when he/she seemed to have below – average competency and, in his point of view, the motivations have more important role than another and it could change the performance of most of language learners no matter how well their aptitude was. This point of view is explained by the idea that motivation not only change learners’ attitude toward languages learning process, but also their interesting about the cultures that these languages belongs to. This makes the learners have another goal to achieve a certain level of second language proficiency beside the classroom result. Therefore, motivation can drive the attention of learners toward the language subject into a more natural and attractive direction and greatly improve their language performance. Beside that, motivation in Gardner, R. C. (2010) was suggested to help learner be more confident in social interaction.

Going with socio-educational model, Gardner, R. C. (2010) also designed the Attitude Motivation Test Battery (AMTB) to qualitatively evaluate the learners’ outcomes in language learning process. There are four variables are evaluated: intergrativeness, attitude toward learning situation, motivation and language anxiety. Each variable is assessed by asking learners to rate its statement in 6-level Likert Scale (from strongly disagree to strongly agree).

Socio-educational model evaluation variables	Reflection	How the AMTB assesses the variable
Intergrativeness	Reflecting the cultural context of target language Determining how open the learners are to ward the target language	Figuring out the extent to which the learners generally interested in Detecting learners’ preset attitude about target language’s community.
Attitude toward learning situation	Educational context and the elements that significantly affect them	Asking learners to evaluate the teachers and other factors of the course.
Motivation	Effective factors that affects both of two contexts	Detecting the learners’ willingness to learn, their attitude toward learning process and how often and effective they receive the motivations and supports in learning process
Language anxiety	The feeling when learners present the speech in target language.	Determining how anxious the learner feels when they presented speech in target language in the classroom or when using the target language in general context.

Another considered theory in this period is from Clement, R. (1980) with Linguistic self-confidence theory. This theory also stated that the factors leading to greater language acquisition involved social context. However, this theory focus on a more specific aspect – the linguistics self-confidence of learners. This theory discussed that this factor is the key for the success of language learners and this can be gained through successfully practicing target language with members of this language community. The success of linguistic practice is based on the learners' perception and the setting of social or practice context. So teachers need to pay attention to both of them.

3.2 The second period: The Cognitive-Situated Period (1990's)

The second period is the time of theories which are flourished from the ground establishing from the previous period. At the first glance, these research seem to criticize and overwrite the result of the previous ones because of their direction to put other aspects to the most important position in language learning motivation phase. In example, Crookes and Schmidt (as cited in MacIntyre, 2002) discussed there were some aspects need to be more considered and there were some aspects need to be moved to less important position. They stated the review on theories they think need to be considered: speech accommodation theory (Giles & Byrnes), acculturation theory (Schumann), monitor model (Krashen) and determinants of motivation (Keller). All of them are considered as the theories focus on the specific context as classroom context and syllabus designing process than the social context. Actually, the theories in this period focus on the linguistics cognition process, they move into how to motivate student by affecting the mental process of learners through classroom activities or setting. This totally doesn't negate the social psychological theories but dig deeper to motivation in specific context.

Contributing to the establishment of Cognitive-Situated theories, Dörnyei (1994) discussed about the three levels of motivation. It included:

- Language level: components in this level inherit the perspective of Gardner, R. C. (2010). This mean it is based the community and social factors to create motivations elements in language learning and teaching process.
- Learners level: this level discusses about the characteristics of learners as traits, aptitude and cognitive processes.
- Learning situation level: this level includes the learning context settings and focus on three main factors (teacher, course, group).

Social constructivist model was a new typical theory in this period. It is the work with the contribution of many researchers: Piaget, J. and Kelly, G. This theory discussed about the constructive nature of the learning process, which mean people tend to actively construct their personal meaning and belief. This can be explained that people have direction to make all of their experiences and practicing in specific context into some rules or systems of rules to establish what they think the world is. Language learners also in the same situation when they are in learning process, they are effected by their cognitive process and learning context. Therefore, this

motivation approach require motivator to consider four elements which affects learners constructive process: teachers, learners, task and context.

Based on the social constructivist model, Marion Williams and Robert L. Burden (1997) develop a framework in attempt to summarize contextual factors can be seen as motivation elements in the table below:

Internal Factors	External Factors
Intrinsic interest of activity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • arousal of curiosity • optimal degree of challenge 	Significant others: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • parents • teachers • peers
Perceived value of activity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • personal relevance • anticipated value of outcomes • intrinsic value attributed to the activity 	The nature of interaction with significant others: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • mediated learning experiences • the nature and amount of feedback • rewards • the nature and amount of appropriate praise • punishments, sanctions
Sense of agency: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • locus of causality • locus of control RE process and outcomes • ability to set appropriate goals 	The learning environment: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • comfort • resources • time of day, week, year • size of class and school • class and school ethos
Mastery <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • feelings of competence • awareness of developing skills and mastery in a chosen area • self-efficacy 	The broader context <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • wider family networks • the local education system • conflicting interest • cultural norms • societal expectations and attitudes

Internal Factors	External Factors
Self-concept <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • realistic awareness of personal strengths and weaknesses in skills required • personal definitions and judgments of success and failure • self-worth concern • learned helplessness 	
Attitudes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to language learning in general • to the target language • to the target language community and culture 	
Other affective states <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • confidence • anxiety, fear 	
Developmental age and stage	
Gender	

3.3 The third period: The Process-Oriented Period

The process oriented period is the most recent period in the evolution of motivation theories. In this period, the direction of motivation research moves into the idea that the motivation should be changed over time to get the highest effect on language learning process. The reason for explaining this idea is that the context of the learning process change continuously and every learner have a different characteristic. There are two typical theories in this period: process model (Dörnyei and Ottó, 2005) and motivational self system (Dörnyei, 2005).

Process model theory was created by Dörnyei and Ottó (2005) as the motivation approach based on three main stage of learning process: the preactional stage, the actional stage, and the postactional stage. Based on the previous research, motivation elements are identified based on the characteristic of each stage.

The stage in language learning	Considered motivation elements
preactional stage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Values involving to language learning process - Learners attitude toward the target language speaking community - Learners' expectation and belief - Supports from environment.
actional stage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quality of target language learning process - The learners' autonomy - Teachers' and parents' effects - the usage of learners self-discipline
postactional stage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biases - Self-concept beliefs - Feedbacks received in language learning process

The motivational self system is a work of Dörnyei (2005) after he conducted the process model theory with Ottó. Also based on the process oriented approach, this theory discussed about three components: the ideal L2 (target language) self, ought-to L2 (target language) self, and L2 (target language) experience. In this system, the ideal L2 self is the expectation the learners want to achieve in future. Therefore, this component plays a very important role in stimulating the learners' interesting toward the language learning process and improving the learner's proficiency. The ought-to self is the image of what students think they should achieve to have no feeling of "being left behind" or disappointing. The ought-to self is the factor help learners keep their morale in a certain rate to avoid demotivation. Finally, the L2 experiences includes the language learning process experiences in learner's life and the effects of situational and environmental aspects.

4 CONCLUSION

The evolution of motivations with language learning have lasted over 40 years from the theory of Gardner. The systematic base of knowledge people collected in this period of time give later researchers, teacher and educators an overview about how language learners performance can be enhanced. By that way, this development significantly changed the world educational system in direction of more and more suitable and effective. In the history of motivation development, the theories move from the simply to the complexity, from the general to specific components, there is a principle that researchers follow: put the learners in the relationship with other aspects of educational context and real context to find the way to enhance the positive effects and reduce the

negative effects of these factors in learner's morale. Nowadays, there is a great development from the beginning of the motivation theories, and many theories, concept and systems are presented. However, the complexity of the learners' characteristics and context make every of them only is suitable for specific cases. To fully apply the motivation in real life context, there are many aspects need to be considered.

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